

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INTERACTIVE DIGITAL SYSTEMS - THE FUTURE OF THE WORLD ECONOMY

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Abstract

In light of the development of the digital economy, new ways for transforming a variable plurality of data and especially systems for their implementation are becoming especially topical. If the ways can be different, so the system must have a row of typical features as in constructive device, so in interactive principle of action. Article is devoted to the description of the created system for implementing the matrix-digital way of transforming a variable plurality of data. In course investigation the typical constructive device of the system was developed, including web-server, proxy-server, server databases, server MySQL, computing server, application server of digital transformation of data, application server of analysis and synthesis, application server of the target appointment, file server; and more optimal software of these servers was defined. For example, the features of the interactive action of the created system were considered, when six temporal networks of subsystems were formed in general network of the system for the performance of each of six stages of the way of the transforming data. The interaction of servers with each other in general network through networks of several subsystems allows to unload and systematize flows of the data which is arriving to each server and come out of it. It is very important, since allows to increase speed of the operational processes at performing the way of transforming data and productivity system. Therefore, the interactive operating principle of the system may become a standard feature for future systems of similar purpose.

Keywords: system, subsystems, way, data, products, digital economy, transformation, process, stages, operations, interactive principle.

Introduction

Every year, digital technologies increasingly enter the life of every person, and the scopes of their application expand. They have no borders or distances, covering all countries of the world and continents. Digital technologies significantly speed up the pace of life and affect the speed of obtaining and processing information and making decisions.

The modern economy is increasingly using advances in the field of artificial intelligence and digital technologies. However, the digital economy is not only and not so much robots, modern computers, automated devices, digital interactive panels and displays. Automated means of processing and obtaining information are only tools of the digital economy.

The transition to a digital economy is a new logic of economic thinking at solving various problems, it is new ways of modeling economic processes and data transformation, it is fundamentally new interactive systems for implementing these ways. Therefore, the economy of the future is a data economy. Thus, the issues of managing the processes of transforming a variable plurality of data are of great topical. As the digital economy develops, the need in new digital ways for analysis, forecast, synthesis, planning, monitoring, adjust a variable plurality of data and systems for their implementation will increase.

Content

Problems of the management by big data arrays are connected with the development of different ways

of the transformation of a variable plurality of data. These ways can be different in dependence from an area of researches, the functional appointment of data and sphere of these application. The processes in the economy are comprehensive and many-sided. Therefore, there can be of many different ways of the transformation of data, since each economic process can be to describe as way containing a list sequency of unique stages, steps and operations regarding the input, transformation and output of a plurality of data.

In different countries of the world, scientific developments and inventions began to appear, describing not only different ways of solving problems, but also systems for their implementation, which are of practical importance for the economy [1-4]. However, all these developments did not operate with data through digital codes, did not offer digital technologies for analysis, forecast, synthesis, generation and optimization of a variable plurality of data.

In the course of the investigation, a way of the matrix-digital transformation of a variable plurality of data was developed and proposed for generating situation-strategic program of the offer of products [5,6].

The way consists in creation in a digital form of a list of the sequences that includes at least six stages, their steps, consecutive operations of each stage and matrix interrelations between them in the form of a chain of the connected matrix-digital models – not less than one model for each stage of the way, these models are connected with each other by the general process

and purpose of the way. The matrix-digital principle of invented way consists not only in the matrix-digital structure of implementing each stage and the way as a whole, but there is in the mechanism of the performance of each stage of the way. The matrix-digital structure of the way is illustrated by matrix-digital models, each of which is constructed for each stage and the way as a whole. These models are illustrated the process of implementing each stage and a way as a whole in digital form, when each stage includes its own steps, which are reflected vertically in form of digital codes, and operations of each step, which are reflected horizontally in the model in form of the digital codes too, but the operations not only are sequentially connected with each other, but also are interrelated vertically with similar operations of other steps of this stage, since they are aimed at the overall result of this stage. Aggregated model of the way characterizes the features interrelations between its stages. Interconnections between operations, steps and stages of the way form as communications between their digital codes that speeds up processing of a variable plurality of data.

The matrix-digital mechanism of the way characterizes by the following features:

firstly, in digital transformation of data, when digital codes, keys of data, barcodes are generated according established parameters for forming interrelations between data in the form of the connected digital codes, keys for automation of various operations of the transformation of data by means of use of an arsenal of the modern technical means;

secondly, in use of matrix mechanisms of the operating processes indissolubly with digital transformation of data. These signs are embodied through the following ways, each of which is a part of invented way, as a whole:

a way of formation of databases over the matrix principle and creation of analog-digital databases for data storage in both a matrix form and digital form;

a way of formation of the object-relational models of DBMS for establishment of matrix-digital interrelations between various type of data;

a way of mutually agreed synthesis of the long-term and current strategies of transformation of data in the system of coordinates of the time and space by means of using a mechanism of the vector analysis;

a way of forecasting data of demand in the system of coordinates of time and space, taking into account the complex of conditions and capabilities of the enterprise, as a result, generating the multidimensional temporal rows of reference data of demand;

a way of generating a plurality of data of the target strategic program of the offer of products and in the uniform system of coordinates of time and space by means of creation in 3D format of the matrix-digital models, and in their using on interactive displays in role of tools for multi-purpose optimization of data;

a way of the situational transformation of a plurality of data on the basis of the matrix-digital models and their using on interactive displays for adjustment of the current data in real time according of the current demand and range of data in the strategic program in order to simulate the different combinations of data, to choice

the optimal combination and to generate a plurality of the output data of the integrated current program, and as the final result, of the way as a whole to generate a situational-strategic program of the offer of products in the form of a synergistic plurality of data.

Modeling the operating processes of implementing the way allows to connect the processes of all stages with each other and orient them on the final result. The performance of all stages of the way in the digital form allows to accelerate the operational processes and processes of the transferring data from server to server, information processing. The matrix mechanism of process of implementing each stage of the way allows to transform all data as a plurality and in the system of coordinates of time and space, when data transform, taking into account their influence at each other and on synergistic result from their plurality and relatively of certain parameters of time and space considered in indissoluble unity; it provides generating the more exact data at both forecasting temporary rows of data of demand and synthesis of strategies and at planning output data of situational-strategic program of the offer of products.

The developed way for generating situational-strategic program of the offer of products is only one of example of way of transforming data. For solution of other tasks connected with transforming data, other ways can be developed. However, in the process of research, not only a way was developed, but also a system that allows not only to implement this way, but also to implement it most quickly and efficiently, because this system is built on a digital principle and is based on the principle of interactive interaction of its elements, it distinguishes this system from well-known analogues [1-4]. The created system has features that make it typical for systems of a similar type and functionality. Let's consider these characteristic features of the system.

Firstly, the structural design of the system must be balanced and include as profile servers, which in accordance with their functional appointment are intended for the performance of the target operations of the way only, so and the profile servers of general functional appointment, such as the web-server, the proxy-server, the controller of the domain, the file server, the application server of digital transformation of data, which perform the service of action of system in a whole, as well as perform typical operations of control, of storage, digital transformation of data and communication processes for transfer of data flows from server to server. Using the specialized servers only increase the speed of the operations with data and data productivity due to these servers have a higher level of automatism in operation, and therefore, are able to perform them more quickly, accurately and reliably.

The feature of the digital system is including of the application server of digital transformation of data in constructive structure of the system, since this server provides the designation of all data by digital codes and for representation of the final documents of the way in digital format.

It is very important for the effectiveness work of the system the controller of domain, which capable to provide the control and the uninterrupted operational

process of all system. For example, in invented system the controller of domain of the fifth generation «Smart RAID V.», of series «Millennium», which is characterized by speed and high fault tolerance, reliability, was used.

A file server has a special role in the structure of any system, because this server is intended to store files of created documents and to transfer data to other servers.

Secondly, the specialized servers, such as server of databases, MySQL server, computing server, the application server of synthesis of strategies or analytical server, also the application server of target appointment have to be among structural elements of a system surely, because:

- server of databases provides the information base for any process, stage, way;
- server MySQL allows to establish the interconnections between different types of data;
- computing server provides calculated operations for any way of data transformation;
- analytical server or application server of strategies synthesis allows to perform the analysis of any type of data and define the direction of transforming data;
- application server of the target appointment performs the target transformation of data to solve the main task of the way.

Thirdly, software of each server has to be compatible to general operating system and to the software of all other servers of the system, and has to use in a certain sequence with other programs, as a result, the software of each server becomes a part of a whole and forms the integrated software of the system in a whole, which does not have analogs over the productivity as the productivity of such software of the system will exceed the productivity of each program used separately.

Fourthly, structure of any system should include interactive panels for displaying data on screens and for monitoring and updating data in real time. For example, interactive SMART displays were used as part of an invented system on the basis of the software «SMART» and with the program for remote access, also with software of servers of the system, it expanded their functionality; they became a necessary element of the multi-function device of the system and were used not only for input, exit, reflection of the information, but also for the analysis, synthesis, forecasting, planning, monitoring and transformation of data. Besides, interactive displays can be used for brain storms, for collective work of developers, it influences quality of the made decisions, promotes increase in accuracy and reliability of the generated program documents.

Fifthly, the system must have of an interactive principle of action, which consists in the formation of not only the general network of the system, but at least more than one subsystem with its own network entering in general network of the system as a whole for more productivity interaction of servers in the network of the system. Each subsystem has to be intended for the performance of a certain stage of the way.

It seems that more optimal interactive network of the system is such network, in which servers of the system are temporarily united for performance of operational and communication processes for implementing the certain stages of the way, because such principle of interaction of servers with each other in general network through networks of several subsystems allows to unload and systematize flows of the data which is arriving to each server and come out of it.

At the same time, each subsystem must have different nature of communications and interaction between elements, because each subsystem will be characterized absolutely by different system of entrances and exits of data, the operating processes, communication interrelations, channels of the movement of the data established for exercise of the purposes of a certain stage of the way. Action of each subsystem include the several levels usually, because each stage of the way contains the several steps, each of which users perform on a certain level of subsystem. Standard characteristic of an interactive system is also that each its subsystem acts during the period of exercise of the operating process by servers only in its own network and has the system of communications between servers in its network, which is coming to an end by the file server storing final files in block of each stage.

In the course investigation was created the interactive system, which included six non-structural and non-hierarchical interactive subsystems for exercise of six stages of the way, each from which was designated as the First subsystem, Second subsystem, Third subsystem, Fourth subsystem, Fifth subsystem, Sixth subsystem. Each of subsystems was intended for the performance of a certain stage of the way and had the several levels on each of which users perform one step of a certain stage. Among constructive elements of each subsystem were as identical servers of the system for performance of typical operations of general appointment, such as the web-server, proxy-server, controller of the domain, the application server of digital transformation of data and file server, so and at least one specialized main server having general functional purpose with a certain subsystem only. The application server of digital transformation of data operates on the basis of software of the «Serial Key Generator» and «Active Barcode» type; file server operates on the basis of software of the «Windows Server 2012 R2 NTFS» type. These servers use its software to perform all stage of the way. Such servers as the computing server, the application server of strategies synth and the application server of the target appointment are equipped by interactive displays of the «SMART Board» type, of series 7000 Pro, which work on the basis of the software «SMART Meeting Pro», «SMART ink» and «SMART TeamWorks, which allow to monitor data in real time, reflect data on screens, to organize brain storms, to have remote access for works with files on different computers the several groups of developers. Level of each subsystem has the target appointment, which corresponds with task of each step of a certain stage of the way, namely: the first, second, third, fourth, fifth, sixth level of each subsystem is intended for performing the operations, respectively on the first, second, third, fourth,

fifth, sixth step of a certain stage of the way and generating the corresponding data relatively a business environment of the company, development strategies of the company, the commodity nomenclature and assortments, the cumulative life cycle of products, quality of products, data of programs of the offer of products.

Let's consider interactive principle of action of created system on an example the constructive device of six subsystem of the system and interaction between them.

The network of the First subsystem unites the following elements: the server of databases with the software of the «Microsoft Excel» type, the application server of digital transformation of data and the file server with their software. The server of databases receives over communication channels from the web-server through the proxy-server constant data for formation of databases and interacts with other servers of the First subsystem that has six levels connected by the general installation, the general process of exercise of the six steps of the first stage of the way. On each level this process is intended for generating the analog-digital database according purpose of a certain step of the first stage of the way, also for forming a digital block of databases, which is a result of implementing all steps of the first stage of the way on all levels of the First subsystem.

The network of the Second subsystem unites the following elements: «MySQL Server» for management by databases with the installed program of the «MySQL» type, as well as the compatible program «MySQL Workbench» that is a tool for the visual and integrated designing and modeling of databases into uniform seamless space owing to establishment of interrelations between them in the system of databases «MySQL», the application server of digital transformation of data and the file server with their software. The server «MySQL», using the program of direct file transfer «FTP Rush» by means of a session «FXP» over the protocol «FTP», receives «csv» files from a block of databases of storage of the file server, in order to carry out import their into installed program «MySQL Workbench», to form the databases management system, also server MySQL interacts with other servers of the Second subsystem that has six levels connected by the general installation, the general process of exercise of the six steps of the second stage of the way. On each level this process is intended for creating object-relational digital model of the databases management system (DBMS) according purpose of a certain step of the second stage of the way, also for forming a digital block of the object-relational models of DBMS, which is a result of implementing all steps of the second stage of the way on all levels of the Second subsystem.

The network of the Third subsystem unites the following elements: the computing server with the software of the «NoSQL» type, as well as of the «IBM SPSS Statistics Standard» and «SAS* Visual Forecasting» type, interactive displays of the «SMART Board» type, the application server of digital transformation of data and the file server with their software. The computing server receives over neural communication channels through proxy-server the variable data of analytical character and receives files from block of databases and from block of the object-relational models of

DBMS of storage of the file server; the computing server uses interactive displays of the «SMART Board» type for operations of analysis, forecast, monitoring of data in real time and interacts with other servers of the Third subsystem that has six levels connected by the general installation, the general process of performing the six steps of the third stage of the way. On each level this process is intended for the creation of temporal rows of forecasted data of demand according purpose of a certain step of the third stage of the way, also for forming an analytical block of data, which is a result of implementing all steps of the third stage of the way on all levels of the Third subsystem.

The network of the Fourth subsystem unites the following elements: the computing server with the software of the «IBM SPSS Statistics Standard» and «SAS* Visual Forecasting» type, the application server of strategies synthesis with the software of the «SAS* Visual Analytics» type, the application server of the digital transformation of data and the file server with their software. The computing server and the application server of strategies synthesis, using the program of direct file transfer «FTP Rush» by means of a session «FXP» over protocol «FTP», receive files from blocks of databases, object-relational models of DBMS and an analytical block of storage of the file server; the computing server and the application server of strategies synthesis, using interactive panels «SMART Board» type, interact with each other and with other servers of the Fourth subsystem that has six levels connected by the general installation, the general process of the performance of the six steps of the fourth stage of the way. On each level this process is intended for synthesis of strategies according purpose of a certain step of the fourth stage of the way, also for forming a digital block of strategies, which is a result of implementing all steps of the fourth stage of the way on all levels of the Fourth subsystem.

The network of the Fifth subsystem unites the following elements: the application server of the target appointment that uses the programs of the «IBM WebSphere Business Modeler» and «Advanced Grapher» type, as well as of the «ZWCAD» type, the computing server with the software of the «IBM SPSS Statistics Standard» and «SAS* Visual Forecasting» type, as well as of the «DecideIT» type, interactive panels of the «SMART Board» type, the application server of the digital transformation of data and the file server with their software. The application server of the target appointment, using program of direct file transfer «FTP Rush» by means of session «FXP» over protocol of «FTP», receives files from blocks of databases and of object-relational models of DBMS, as well as from an analytical block and a block of strategies of storage of the file server; the computing server and the application server of target appointment, using interactive panels of the «SMART Board» type, simulate on screens models of assortments, life cycles, quality and the offer of products, interact with each other and with other servers of the Fifth subsystem that has four levels connected by the general installation, the general process of performing the four steps of the fifth stage of the way. On each level this process is intended for planning and generating a plurality of the output data of the target strategic program of the offer of products in interrelation with

temporal and spatial parameters according purpose of a certain step of the fifth stage of the way, also for forming a digital block of strategic programs, which is a result of implementing all steps of the fifth stage of the way on all levels of the Fifth subsystem.

The network of the Sixth subsystem unites the following elements: the application server of the target appointment that uses the programs of the «IBM WebSphere Business Modeler» and «Advanced Grapher» type, as well as of the «ZWCAD» type, the computing server with the software of type «IBM SPSS Statistics Standard» and of the «SAS* Visual Forecasting» type, as well as of the «DecideIT» type, interactive panels of the «SMART Board» type, the application server of the digital transformation of data and the file server with their software. The application server of target appointment, using the program of direct file transfer «FTP Rush» by means of a session «FXP» over the protocol «FTP», receives files from a block of the strategic programs of storage of the file server; the computing server and the application server of the target appointment, using interactive displays of the «SMART Board» type, monitor data in real time, reflect the situational models on the screens for adjustment of data, they interact with each other and with other servers of the Sixth subsystem, which has four levels connected by the general installation, the general process of performance of the four steps of the sixth stage of the way. On each level this process is intended for situational transformation of a plurality of the output data of current programs of the offer of products according purpose of a certain step of the sixth stage of the way, also for forming a digital block of the situational-strategic program, which is a result of implementing all steps of the sixth stage of the way on all levels of the Sixth subsystem.

Action of the network of the each subsystem consists in work of servers of this subsystem implementing the operating processes, consisting in the consecutive performance of operations of each step of a certain stage of the way, and the communication processes, consisting in procedures of an entrance and exit from operating process on each of servers and in their interaction with each other by means of communication channels for transfer of a data flow received as a result of their operating process at the performance of the steps of a certain stage of the way at the levels of a certain subsystem.

Upon termination of all operations at all levels of Sixth subsystem and finishing the sixth stage of the way by the formation of a digital block of the situational-strategic program, which is a result of work of servers not only of the Sixth subsystem but system in a whole, the interaction of structural elements in the network of the Sixth subsystem and system as a whole comes to an end.

All created subsystems interact with each other through the file server regarding of transferring data from a certain data block of the storage of the file server of one subsystem to the servers of other subsystems, since users used the data creating during the execution of a certain stage of the way, as a result of the operational process of servers in the network of this subsystem, in the process of generating other data, at performance of subsequent stages of the way by servers in the

network of other subsystems. Therefore, mechanism of connection of all subsystems with each other in uniform network of the system was implemented.

The created interactive mechanism of action of the system is very important for increase of productivity of the system, since promotes increase in flexibility, maneuverability of the system, reduction of time of transition from operation to operation, as well as duration of transfer of data over communication channels.

Conclusion

The developed system can be classified as a digital system, because, firstly, the system itself is built on a digital basis, and secondly, the system is intended for implementing a digital way for transforming a variable plurality of data. This system is simple in the creation and using, includes servers that have compatible software and due to interactive principle of action, the system is flexible, maneuverable, productive, economical, and does not require large implementation costs. Therefore, the system may be in wide demand in various industries in market economies around the world. The above-mentioned features of the created system can serve as the basis for the formation of systems of this type and functionality. The invented system and a way of the data transformation open a new page in science and take a big step into the world of the digital economy.

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